

Disagreement diary of: “Onboarding in Variant-rich System Development: Voices from the Trenches”

Extractors:

Maidier Azanza

Arantza Irastorza

Raul Medeiros

Iteration: 1

Documents: Txindoki

Date: 26/04/22

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	Nº of codes	Nº of quotations
Raul (Coder 1)	27	22
Arantza (Coder 2)	33	13
Maider (Coder 3)	38	22

Code	Old name	New name
S06	Friendly team	Friendly atmosphere
B09	—	Lack of structured documentation
C01	Age range	SPL lifespan
C06	SPL history time	—
C09		Adoption reluctance
C10		Adoption time

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	Nº of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	1:3	Three different codes: A01, C05 and C08	3	Lack of context. Broaden quote.	A01
Quote	1:6	Two different codes: B03 and C04	3	Lack of context. Broaden quote. It refers to motivation for SPL	C04
Quote	1:10	Two different codes: B01 and B08	3	Quote is too broad and mentions two problems.	Divide quote in two. 1:10 with code B08 and 1:63 with code B01
Quote	1:11	Two different codes: C05 and S02	3	While it does talk about how products are developed, it mainly refers to version control systems	S02
Quote	1:12	Two different codes: B02 and S06	3	Both codes refer to similar things. One thing is how compatible the newcomer is with the team, the other how helpful the team is in general.	B02 for the quote. Rename S06 to reflect the importance of a helping atmosphere of the team.
Quote	1:49	Three different codes: S01, S03, S10	3	It refers to documentation, S03 is the most specific	S03
Quote	1:14	Quote too broad	3	Quote too broad, it refers to two different things.	Create quotes 1:26 and 1:27 with codes S07 and S05 respectively.
Quote	1:16	Two different codes: B07 and S10	3	Quote too broad, it refers to two different things.	Create quote 1:64 with code S10. Create quote B09. Broaden quote 1:16 and assign

					B09.
Quote	1:28	Two different codes: C01 and C06	2	Both codes actually are meant to refer to the same concept.	Rename C01 to reflect a more precise meaning. Delete C06
Quote	1:29 1:30 and 1:46	All quotes have the same code	2	All quotes refer to the same concept.	Merge quotes
Quote	1:31 and 1:50	One coder marked a broader quote. All have the same code.	3	The broader quote provides more context	Merge quotes
Quote	1:33 and 1:54	One coder marked a broader quote. All have the same code.	2	The broader quote provides more context	Merge quotes
Quote	1:35	Two different codes: S01 and S07	2	The sentence refers to two separate strategies	Create quote 1:65 for S07. Mark 1:35 with S01.
Quote	1:41	Other coders did not agree	1	The sentence refers to two different issues.	Mark the first part with C04 and create a new code (C09) for the second part.
Quote	1:43	Other coders did not agree	1	The sentence does not refer to adoption.	Mark with C04
Quote	1:44	Other coders did not agree	1	The quote is too vague	Delete quote
Quote	1:45	Other coders did not agree	1	The quote is linked to another quote in the same paragraph	Lengthen quote 1:21 to cover this quote
Quote	1:47	Other coders did not agree	1	It is not clear whether the quote refers to the SPL or an example. It refers mainly to how work is divided in the team, which is captured	Delete quote

				in a previous quote	
Quote	1:51	Other coders did not agree	1	The same idea is captured exactly by quote 1:9 just above	Delete quote
Quote	1:58	Other coders did not agree	1	The sentence refers to two different issues.	Shorten the quote. Create a new quote with the second part and mark it with C05
Quote	1:59	Other coders did not agree	1	The quote is too vague	Delete quote
Quote	1:60	Other coders did not agree	1	The quote refers to another issue	Create a new code for it (C10)

Iteration: 2
Documents: Aizkorri

Date: 12/05/22

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	N° of codes	N° of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	17	33
Raul (Coder 2)	22	9
Maider (Coder 3)	24	2

Code	Old name	New name
	Newcomer profile	Newcomer experience level
S12	Optional of familiar technology	Leverage on previous knowledge

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	N° of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	2:1	Two different codes: C03 and C07	3	The quote is more about the implementation than the domain itself. Similar to the sentence that follows it.	Merge S:1 and S:40 and assign C07
Quote	2:8	Three different codes: C03, C06 and C07	3	The quote covers two issues.	Divide the quote, assign C03 to the first part and C07 to the second
Quote	2:12	Two different codes B04 and "Newcomer profile"	3	Whether or not, Newcomer profile is too general and needs specialization. After a following discussion on what B04 and B11 mean and how to differentiate between them, the decision is changed to B11.	Assign B11 to this quote.
Quote	2:16	Three different codes S07, B11 and "Ideas for aid tools"	3	The first part refers to what they wish they have. The second refers to what technical knowledge newcomers lack.	Assign "ideas for aid tools" to the first part of the quote
Quote	2:20	Two different codes, B11 and "newcomer profile"	3	As discussed above, both can overlap. Newcomer's profile will be specialized in how much experience newcomers have. B11 is more precise.	Assign B11 to the quote. Merge it with the second part of 2:16 that was left out on the previous discussion.
Quote	2:19	Three different codes, "newcomer profile", B01 and B05	3	B01 does not apply. Newcomer profile is too general, we need to decide on what we want to gather.	Assign B05 to the quote,
Quote	2:21	The quote was enlarged by a following coder (quote 2:42)	3	2:42 provides more context.	Merge both quotes.
Quote	2:22	Only the first coder	1	The following coders overlooked the quote	Assign "newcomer experience level"

Quote	2:23	Two codes C02 and "newcomer profile"	2	The answer actually states what they don't do.	Remove quote.
Quote	2:27	Three codes H03, "newcomer profile" and S12	3	"Newcomer profile" is discarded as too general (see change of name in the table). Between H03 and S12 both are mentioned.	Assign S12 to 2:27. Create a new quote with the previous sentence with H03.
Quote	2:31	Two codes B09 and S10	2	The quote states that they don't have specific documentation for newcomers	Assign B09
Quote	2:32	Two quotes S07 and S09	3	It states the idea of giving small tasks to newcomers	Assign S09
Quote	2:34	Three quotes B09, S10 and "ideas for aid tools"	3	The quote refers to both what documentation they have and what would be desirable.	Change quote 2:34 and assign S10 and create quote 2:53 to reflect the part of "ideas for aid tools"
Quote	2:36	Two quotes, B10 and S09	3	The quote states that they don't have a specific onboarding procedure and that they give the current problem	Assign B10
Quote	2:38	Three codes A02, C05 and C07	3	Mainly refers to how code is added to products	Assign A02
Quote	2:41	Two codes A02 and C05	2	The same case as quote 2.38	Assign A02
Quote	2:48	Two codes B10 and S08	2	The quote refers to not having an onboarding plan	Assign S08

Iteration: 3
Documents: Saioa

Date: 06/06/22

Meeting type:

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	Nº of codes	Nº of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	28	80
Raul (Coder 2)	35	6
Maider (Coder 3)	34	14

Code	Old name	New name
C13		SPL Maturity
H05		In-house onboarding
S15		Balanced Senior/Junior ratio

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	N° of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	3.6	Two different codes, C03 and C08.	3	C08 refers to the size of the software, this entails the complexity of the domain. A note is added to the codebook to describe C08 more precisely.	Assign C03
Quote	3.7	Two different codes, C08 and B12	3	Following the discussion on 3.6, it refers to the domain	Assign B12
Quote	3.8	Two different codes, C03 and C08	3	Following the same discussion, it describes that the second department has one half of the requirements	Assign C08
Quote	3.12	Two different codes, A02 and C04	3	It describes how they have clients requiring customizations	Assign C04
Quote	3.13	Two different codes, C05 and C07	3	It describes how a product is certified and specifically refers to how clients might ask for customizations. Add note to C07 to specify that it refers to technologies used to implement the SPL.	Assign C05
Quote	3.14	Two different codes, A03 and C05	3	Both codes are applicable, and belong to different semantic domains	Keep both codes
Quote	3.15	Two different codes, C04 and C10	3	Discussion on nuances between C01, C04 and C10. Notes added to the codebook. In this case, it refers to why they decided to manage variability in some way.	Assign C04
Quote	3.16	Two different codes, C01 and C07	2	It refers to how they have a series of	Create a new code, C13, that

				processes to realize variability	refers to the maturity of the SPL
Quote	3.17	Two different codes, C01 and C07	3	It refers to potential tools. DOORS was mentioned in the previous sentence	Enlarge the quote to cover DOORS too and assign C07
Quote	3.18	Two different codes, C01 and C07	3	It refers to architecture and processes, C07 was too narrow and did not cover it.	Assign C07. Add a note to indicate that it covers technologies, architecture and other artefacts that are part of the development process.
Quote	3.19	Three different codes, C01, C09 and C12	3	It indicates how they manage variability, with their own processes, as the volume is not too big.	Following the discussion above, assign C07 and see in the rest of the codes if C12 can be deleted as it overlaps with the former
Quote	3.20	Three different codes, C01, C04 and C07	3	It describes their own variability model	Following the above, assign C07
Quote	3.21	Two different codes, C03 and C04	3	It describes the motivation for their work in the domain, not the motivation for the SPL	Assign C03
Quote	3.22	Two different codes, C01 and C04	2	It describes their current state in the domain	Delete quote
Quote	3.23	Three different codes, A01, A04 and C01	3	It describes how they created the variability	Assign A04
Quote	3.24	Three different codes, A02, C01 and C03	3	It describes some developments they are doing in certain parts of the domain	Assign C03
Quote	3.27	Three different codes, C01, C07 and C12	3	Based on the discussion above, it refers to the SPL implementation	Assign C07 and merge quote with 3.92
Quote	3.28	Three different codes, C01, C07 and C12	3	Same discussion	Assign C07

Quote	3.29	Three different codes, B12, H01 and "Hiring needs"	3	The quote talks about B12 and H01, "Hiring needs" is mentioned later, one or two persons a year	Divide the quote in three, one for each code
Quote	3.35	Two different codes, C02 and "Hiring needs"	2	It describes when people from the development team transfer to other departments, in-house onboarding	Create a new code "H05: in-house onboarding"
Quote	3.36	Two different codes, C02 and S06	3	It refers to the atmosphere of the team, how helpful it is	Assign S06
Quote	3.37	Two different codes, C02 and S06	3	Same discussion as above	Assign S06
Quote	3.40	Three different codes B11, B12 and B13	3	It refers to lack of technical knowledge and lack of knowledge about processes	Assign the first part to B11 and the last to B13 (3.82)
Quote	3.41	Two coders coded ramp-up time and one suggested deleting the code	2	It refers to one factor that might affect the ramp-up time	Assign ramp-up time and
Quote	3.42	Two different codes, B02 and B12	2	It refers to coordination issues in general	Delete quote
Quote	3.43	Two different codes, B12 and B13	3	Both 3.43 and 3.44 refer to the same issue. It refers more to the development	Merge both quotes and assign B13.
Quote	3.45	Two different codes, B04 and B12	3	The quote combines issues with the process and the domain.	Assign B13. Create a new quote 3.103 with a B04 with the following sentence that summarizes that idea.
Quote	3.46	Two different codes, S09 and S16	3	It refers to the first scoped tasks for a newcomer	Assign S09
Quote	3.49	Two different codes, S07 and S08	3	It refers how a mentor is assigned the first day	Assign S07
Quote	3.51	Two different codes, B01 and S08	3	It refers to both	Keep both codes

Quote	3.54	Two different codes, S06 and S13	3	It is more than a helping atmosphere, it refers to sharing goals.	Assign S13
Quote	3.55	Two different codes, S13 and S17	3	Sharing the goals was understood by both as company/product goals or more generally as goals for all involved stakeholders.	Assign S13 understanding that it refers also to the goals expected for the newcomer.
Quote	3.56	Two different codes, S07 and S14	3	While it mentions mentoring, it refers more to how the newcomer tasks need to be aligned with the general development aims	Assign S14
Quote	3.58	Two different codes, S09 and S12	3	It refers to how it is easier if they are comfortable	Assign S12
Quote	3.59	Two different codes, S04 and S15	3	It refers to courses	Assign S04
Quote	3.61	Two different codes, B01 and B09	3	More about the documentation	Assign B09
Quote	3.62	Two different codes, S10 and Idea for aid tools	3	It refers to different abstraction levels of technical documentation. Note added to indicate that S10 covers all.	Assign S10
Quote	3.63	Four different codes B05, B06, S03 and S10.	3	It refers to both how newcomers need to be independent and that they have documentation at hand.	Assign B05 and S10
Quote	3.64	Two different codes, S10 and Idea for aid tools	3	It refers to both	Keep both codes
Quote	3.68	Two different codes, S14 and S16	3	It refers to how if newcomers are dealing with a task that is of interest to the team, it is easier for more senior developer to dedicate time to them.	Assign S14
Quote	3.69	Two different codes, C11 and Hiring Context	3	Both codes at the end refer to the same idea	Assign C11 and delete Hiring Context

Quote	3.70	Two different codes, C11 and Hiring Context	3	Both codes at the end refer to the same idea	Assign C11 and delete Hiring Context
Quote	3.71	Three different codes, C02, C11 and Hiring Needs	3	It refers to hiring in the COVID context. C11 and Hiring needs overlap (candidate for deleting)	Assign C11
Quote	3.72	Two different codes, S10 and Ideas for aid tools	3	It refers to both	Keep both codes
Quote	3.79	Three different codes, B12, S08 and S15	3	None captures well the idea	Assign S06
Quote	3.100	Coded with S04	1	It refers more to how newcomers are guided	Assign S08
Quote	3.101	Coded with C02	1	It also describes how the teams should combine experienced/not experienced developers	Assign C02 and create S15

Iteration: 4
Documents: Usurbe

Date: 23/06/22

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	N° of codes	N° of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	20	32
Maider (Coder 2)	15	0
Raul (Coder 3)	19	2

Code	Old name	New name
C05	Product derivation strategy	Variability management strategy

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	Nº of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	4.3	Two different codes, C02 and C03	3	The quote refers to both, first one and then the other.	Divide the quote in two (4.3 and 4.35), assign C03 to the first part and C02 to the second.
Quote	4.4	Two codes A01 and A04 and C07	3	It refers to how the system is created and gives details about architecture, functionality design, etc. On how the system was created, it mentions how new needs fuel the development.	Assign A04 and C07
Quote	4.5	Two codes C03 and C07	3	It gives details on how many products they have, how the domain is.	Assign C03.
Quote	4.6	Two codes C02 and C07	3	The first part refers to how teams work, the second gives details on the implementation.	Assign C02 to the first part and C07 to the second (4.33)
Quote	4.7	Two codes A03 and C07	3	It gives little detail about the implementation. It sets the ground for the following discussion on how the products are developed.	Delete quote
Quote	4.8	Two codes A03 and C07	3	It gives details on how the product is constructed, how the same binary is always installed.	Assign C07
Quote	4.10	Three codes A03, C05 and C07	3	Discussion on C05, whether it refers to the product derivation itself, or it should also cover the variability management. All quotes assigned to this code are revised, and the name is changed to "Variability management strategy".	Assign C05

Quote	4.11	Three codes A03, C05 and C07	3	Based on the discussion above, C05.	Assign C05
Quote	4.14	Two codes B04 and H04	3	H04 is tangential at best. It refers to how the developers that have been incorporated to the team didn't have domain knowledge	Assign B04
Quote	4.15	Two codes B04 and C07	3	It describes how the complexity of the implementation can be too big to grasp at first.	Assign B01 and C07
Quote	4.17	Three codes B01, B11 and B12	3	It starts on how complex the system is and the cognitive overload it brings to the newcomer	Assign B01
Quote	4.18	Two codes B01, B08	3	It refers to how newcomers can feel at the beginning, fear of breaking the system	Assign B01
Quote	4.19	Three codes B05, B08 and S07	3	It refers to how newcomers can have fear doing things	Assign B05
Quote	4.25	Two codes S09 and S14	3	Discussion on what S14 means and what constitutes S14. It needs to be a task that is of particular interest to the team, so that they don't mind the time dedicated to the newcomer that much.	Assign S09
Quote	4.30	Three codes S09, S16 and Ideas for aid tools	3	The quote is ambiguous, it doesn't answer the question.	Delete quote.
Quote	4.32	Two codes S09 and S14	3	Based on the previous discussion on S14, it does not apply.	Assign S09

Iteration: 5
Documents: Izazpi

Date: 08/07/22

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	Nº of codes	Nº of quotations
Raul (Coder 1)	26	41
Maider (Coder 2)	20	2
Arantza (Coder 3)	25	0

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	Nº of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	5.2	Two codes C03 and C07	3	It comments on OSs, it refers to domain in its broader sense	Assign C03
Quote	5.3	Two codes C03 and C06	3	It comments when and how is the variability enacted	Assign C05

Quote	5.7	Two codes C04 and C05	3	The quote states what they have now, to then comment on the variability that they foresee in the future	Assign C04
Quote	5.8	Two codes C01 and C13	3	The quote refers to how long they have been developing the products, less on how developed the SPL is	Assign C01
Quote	5.15	Two codes B09 and S05	3	The quote refers to how it is difficult to find certain information. The following quote refers to how mentors can guide in this process.	Merge quotes 5.15 and 5.16 and assign B09 and S07 to them
Quote	5.18	Three codes C02, H05 and S06	3	The quote refers to how the physical configuration of the office fosters communication among the team members	Assign C02 and S06
Quote	5.21	Two codes B01 and B12	3	The quote refers to the fact that the domain has a lot of information	Assign B12
Quote	5.27	Four codes B10, B11, C11 and S04	3	The quote comments how the lack of technical knowledge of the company itself affects the onboarding, as there is none with the knowledge in the company and has to look for knowledge outside	Assign B11 and S04
Quote	5.31	Three codes B12, S06 and Onboarding and variability specificity	3	It does not refer to strategies	Assign B12 and Onboarding and variability specificity
Quote	5.37	Three codes S06, S13 and C03	3	It refers to how newcomers should have a direct interaction with end-users to see how the product impacts them.	Divide the quote in two (5.37 and 5.44), one with S06 and C03 and the other with S13 and C03.
Quote	5.42	Two codes S06 and S14	3	The quote mentions how it is interesting to integrate newcomers in team discussions because they provide a fresh perspective	Create new code S16 and assign it.

Quote	5.38	Two codes S06 and S14	3	Same as the quote before	Assign S16
Quote	5.43	Two codes S05 and S10	3	The question wants to confirm if they provide end-user documentation apart from the technical one	Merge 5.43 and 5.39 and assign S05

Iteration: 6
Documents: Ernio

Date: 19/09/22

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	N° of codes	N° of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	29	43
Maider (Coder 2)	19	43
Raul (Coder 3)	22	43

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	N° of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	6.2	Two codes C03 and C07	3	It mentions technologies, more than domain itself.	Assign C07
Quote	6.3	Two codes C03 and C07	3	While it mentions Javascript, it refers to process automation, pertaining to the domain.	Assign C03

Quote	6.5	Two codes C02 and C03	3	It refers to the new incorporations to the team	Assign C02
Quote	6.7	Two codes C03 and C04	3	It describes why they have the need to manage variability	Assign C04
Quote	6.8	Three codes C03, C04 and C05	3	It describes why the need to have different versions for each company	Assign C04
Quote	6.9	Two codes A03, and A04	3	It does not refer to adoption specifically, leave only the variability management code	Leave C05
Quote	6.38	Two codes A01, and C07	3	It comments on how they needed to modernize the system and how they created the core from which the different versions were created.	Assign C04
Quote	6.18	Two codes H04, and Hiring needs	3	It refers to the last hiring experiences	Assign H04
Quote	6.20	Two codes S03, and S10	3	S10 is broader, but the quote refers to coding best practices	Assign S03
Quote	6.21	Two codes B11, and B13	3	It does mention the development environment but it pertains to how the branches are organized, how the development processes are in the organization.	Assign B13
Quote	6.22	Two codes B10, and B09	3	The quote is in response to a question about documentation	Assign B09
Quote	6.23	Two codes B01, and B09	3	The quote mentions how too much documentation can make the newcomer feel overwhelmed	Assign B01
Quote	6.24	Three codes H01, B03 and C02	3	The quote mentions how they hired another company to develop part of their software	Assign H01
Quote	6.29	Two codes B04, and B13	3	It mentions business processes	Assign B13

Quote	6.31	Two codes B04, and S12	3	The quote talks about issues with the domain. It mentions previous knowledge, but only regarding eclipse	Assign B04
Quote	6.41	Two codes B04, and S05	3	The quote mentions the basic concepts a newcomer needs understand	Assign B04
Quote	6.35	Three codes B04, B13 and Ideas for aid tools	3	The quote mentions how too much documentation can make the newcomer feel overwhelmed	Assign Ideas for aid tools

Iteration: 7
Documents: Murumendi

Date: 20/09/22

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	Nº of codes	Nº of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	31	37
Maider (Coder 2)	20	37
Raul (Coder 3)	22	37

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	Nº of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	7.3	Two codes C04, and C07	3	It describes why they opted for standardization and explicit variability management	Assign C04
Quote	7.7	Four codes A01, A02, C04 and C05	3	Regarding adoption, they did start with clone&own but have applied an extractive approach. It also describes that in that moment	Assign A01 Assign C04

				they had issues with inconsistencies and hence the extraction and standardization processes.	
Quote	7.6	Three codes C07, C12 and C05	3	It describes what tool they use to manage variability	Assign C12
Quote	7.8	Two codes C05 and C07	3	It describes how requirements are implemented, catering for variability	Assign C07
Quote	7.9	Three codes A01, C05 and C13	3	It describes how they created the SPL and the common platform they have, how evolved their SPL is	Assign A01 and C13
Quote	7.10	Two codes C02, and C13	3	It describes their SPL development team	Assign C02
Quote	7.11	Three codes C04, C07 and C13	3	It describes that they had a person who had the time to standardize and dedicate time to create the core	Assign C04
Quote	7.37	Two codes C01 and C10	3	Two overlapping quotes, 7.12 and 7.36. The former is shorter. Keep the second as it has more context. It states how long it is since they started to manage the variability	Assign C01
Quote	7.21	Two codes B09, and B10	3	It refers to their lack of explicit documentation for onboarding.	Assign B10
Quote	7.22	Two codes S04, and S08	3	It says that they do not have an explicit and documented orientation plan, but this plan exists and the interviewee is the person responsible for it	Assign S08
Quote	7.23	Two codes B11, and S04	3	It comments on the courses they have created for newcomers	Assign S04

Quote	7.24	Two codes S04, and S10	3	It describes the technical documentation they have created	Assign S10
Quote	7.24	Code B11		It describes issues related to the processes of mindset change	Reduce the quote and create a new quote 7.38 with code B14
Quote	7.24	Two codes B11, and S10	3	It describes the technical issues the newcomers encounter	Assign B11
Quote	7.26	Three codes S05, S09 and S14	3	It describes their first tasks, validation tasks from the point of view of the user.	Assign S09. Combine with 7.27
Quote	7.28	Two codes S07, and S06	3	It describes how they guide newcomers and how they assign mentors	Assign S07
Quote	7.33	Two codes S10 and Ideas for aid tools	3	It describes their wish, not a current strategy	Assign Ideas for aid tools
Quote	7.34	Two codes S06, and S11	3	It describes how a newcomer on their own is not enough, needs contact with the rest of the team	Assign S06

Iteration: 8
Documents: Ganboa

Date: 22/09/2022

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	Nº of codes	Nº of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	36	60
Maider (Coder 2)	25	60
Raul (Coder 3)	28	60

Code	Old name	New name
S03	Coding best practices	Good practices documentation

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	N° of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	8.5	Three codes, A01, C04 and C13	3	It describes how the product line started, why they started managing variability starting from two different products.	Assign A01 and C04.
Quote	8.4	Three codes, C04, C07 and C09	3	It describes how and why they started with variability, but using configuration.	Assign C04
Quote	8.3	Two codes, C01, and C10	2	It describes how long it took to refactor and start managing variability explicitly	Assign C13
Quote	8.6	Two codes, C01, and C13	3	It describes how long it's been since they started from the two separate products	Assign C01
Quote	8.9	Two codes, C05, and C07	3	It describes how variability is managed in the implementation, C05 is more precise.	Assign C05
Quote	8.10	Three codes, C04, C05, and B12	3	It described why they went from a purely configuration model to explicit variability management and how it was a person doing the capstone project having the issues.	Assign C04 and B12
Quote	8.12	Three codes, A03, C04, and C05	3	It describes why they left their initial 150% approach	Assign C04 and A03
Quote	8.18	Two codes, B12 and onboarding and variability specificities	3	It describes how variability can be a barrier	Assign onboarding and variability specificities
Quote	8.19	8.19, 8.20 and 8.21 are different quotes, that have the very same codes C02 and H05	3	All the quotes are actually describing the team and how in-house onboarding is carried out.	Merge the three quotes and assign C02 and H05.

Quote	8.22	Three codes, C02, H01 and Hiring needs	3	The quote describes incorporations to the team.	Assign H01 and hiring needs
Quote	8.23	Two codes C11 and H01	3	It describes how they subcontract parts of the development.	Assign H01
Quote	8.24	Three codes C11, S09, and S14	3	It does refer to giving newcomers tasks they have interest in but do not have time to carry them out. Same reasoning as the one described in Saioa but with weaker links with the newcomer	Assign S14
Quote	8.27	Two codes C02 and hiring needs	3	The quote refers to how big the team is, including subcontractors. But it does not specify how many of the latter need onboarding.	Assign C02
Quote	8.30	Three codes C02, Interviewee, H05	3	The quote refers to how they can change departments in the company and how it helps getting a broader view. The interviewee had such experience.	Assign H05 and Interviewee.
Quote	8.31	Two codes B11, and B01	3	It describes issues newcomers may have with the new tool. 8.32 has the same codes and describes issues with the installation.	Merge both quotes and assign B11.
Quote	8.34	Two codes S04, and S10	3	It describes the documentation she has created for newcomers	Assign S10
Quote	8.35	Two codes S09, and B11	3	It describes how the variability management tool is new for the developers and how she had to create documentation specific for them to use it	Assign onboarding and variability specificities.
Quote	8.34	Two codes S04, and S10	3	It describes the documentation she has created for newcomers	Assign S10

Quote	8.38	Two codes S03, and S10	3	It describes that they have technical documentation but also how they have best practices for modelling	Divide the quote and assign S10 to the first and S03 to the second.
Quote	8.39	Three codes C01, S09, and S10	3	It describes how they have documentation and how they ask newcomers to write small and concrete parts that are later revised by others.	Assign S09
Quote	8.40	Two codes S03, and S10	3	It describes best practices	Assign S03
Quote	8.43	Two codes S08, and S09	2	It describes how they give tasks in a certain order to ease onboarding	Assign S08
Quote	8.44	Two codes S07, and S06	3	It describes that they do not have a specific mentor but that they can always ask different members of the team.	Assign S06
Quote	8.47	Three codes B04, B12, and S09	3	Apart from the first scoped tasks of the newcomer, it describes how parts are abstract and complex and still difficult to understand for the interviewee despite her experience.	Assign S09 and B12
Quote	8.48	Three codes C07, B12, and S09	3	It mainly describes how they have modularized the implementation and traced it from requirements.	Assign C07
Quote	8.49	Two codes C07, C13	2	It describes how the architecture has evolved and how they have been refactoring to obtain an architecture that is both modular and trazable from requirements	Assign C07
Quote	8.51	Two codes S03, and S10	3	It describes how subcontractors need examples or good practices to be able to perform their job	Assign S03
Quote	8.52	Three codes S08, S10, and Ramp-up time	3	It describes how they assume that the	Assign Ramp-up time

				newcomer needs at least two months of a purely learning phase before really diving into the work.	
Quote	8.53	Two codes S08, and S10	3	It describes their lifecycle and how it guides the first tasks the newcomers have to do.	Assign S08
Quote	8.54	Three codes B01, S08, and S10	3	In these first tasks, it tells how newcomers may need to deal with a great deal of documentation and can get scared.	Assign B01 and S08
Quote	8.55	Two codes B01, and S10	3	While it can be implicit, it does not explicitly state that newcomers can feel overwhelmed	Assign S10
Quote	8.59	Two codes B09, and Ideas for aid tools	3	It describes how they do have the documentation, but it is sometimes very costly to locate what you are looking for.	Assign B09

Iteration: 10
Documents: Ausagztelu

Date: 10/01/2023

Attendees: Arantza, Maider and Raul

Overview	N° of codes	N° of quotations
Arantza (Coder 1)	32	0
Maider (Coder 2)	32	0
Raul (Coder 3)	30	73

Type (code/quote)	Id.	Disagreement	N° of Coders	Discussion	Decision
Quote	11.4	Two codes C03, and C04	3	It does mention the motivation but it pertains mainly to domain.	Assign C03
Quote	11.8	Three codes C03, C04 and A01	3	It describes the domain but mainly why it is a good case to implement variability	Assign C04

Quote	11.46	Three codes C03, C04 and C07	3	While it mentions the domain and the implementation technology, it mainly describes why they created the SPL	Assign C04
Quote	11.12	Two codes C03 and C05	3	It mentions both in the same quote.	Assign C03 to the first part and create 11.74 with the second part and assign C05
Quote	11.18	Two codes, Hiring needs and interviewee	3	It specifically mentions in how many onboardings has each interviewee been involved	Assign interviewee
Quote	11.64	Four codes C01, C04, C13 and A01	3	It describes a focal point of the development of the SPL.	Assign C01
Quote	11.14	Two codes C05 and C07	3	It describes how the variability management is implemented	Assign C05
Quote	11.15	Two codes C05 and C03	3	It describes aspects of the variability and the domain, but it refers to how products need to be customized once after they are derived from the SPL	Assign C13
Quote	11.65	Three codes A01, C01 and C02	3	The quote mentions both C01 and A01 but in different sentences	Divide the quote in two, creating 11.75, and assign A01 and C01 respectively
Quote	11.19	Two codes C02 and Hiring needs	3	It mentions the people involved in the development	Assign C02
Quote	11.20	Two codes C02 and Interviewee	3	It describes how newcomers start with small tasks in the products	Assign S18
Quote	11.24	H03 and Newcomer experience level	3	From the previous context H03 makes sense but the quote exclusively refers to the latter	Assign Newcomer experience level

Quote	11.26	B01, B11, Onboarding & Variability	3	It refers how they can feel scared when they see all the code plus the annotations	Assign B01 and Onboarding & Variability
Quote	11.27	B01, B05 and Newcomer experience level	3	While it does mention how some newcomers can feel scared, it describes how some people are more daring than others	Assign B05
Quote	11.66	Two codes, B08 and B11	3	It mentions how abstraction is needed to fully understand the SPL	Assign B14
Quote	11.30	Two codes, B08 and ramp-up time	3	It does not specify the ramp-up time. It refers to how the task can be too complex.	Assign B08
Quote	11.67	Three codes, B11, C07 and C12	3	It mentions the technologies that are used in the SPL implementation	Assign C07
Quote	11.31	Two codes, B11 and S12	3	It mentions the problems of developers that did not know Javascript previously	Assign B11
Quote	11.33	B01, B11, Onboarding&Variability	3	It mentions the lack of technical experience and the issues it brings when debugging	Enlarge quote and assign B11 and Onboarding&Variability
Quote	11.35	B03, B09, S10	3	It mentions how some documentation that was created for newcomers, was not shared with the rest of the team and, hence, effectively did not exist.	Assign B03 and S10
Quote	11.36	B12, C12, Onboarding&Variability	3	It does not mention the domain, it is more how the problems with the tooling due to variability affect onboarding	Assign C12 and Onboarding&Variability
Quote	11.37	B12, C12, Onboarding&Variability	3	Same as the one before but with more technical details	Assign C12 and Onboarding&Variability
Quote	11.38	B04, B12, Onboarding&Variability			Mindset change, onboarding and variability specificities

Quote	11.40	S12, H05	3	It mentions that all newcomers start modifying products before working on the platform. Needs to be checked if this is the case for others.	Assign S18 and H05
Quote	11.69	Three codes B04, B11 and B12	3	Looking more closely at the mentioned acronyms, it refers to technical knowledge.	Assign B11
Quote	11.39	Three codes S09, S10, S12	3	It mentions how they provide models and papers to newcomers	Assign S10
Quote	11.41	One code S04	1	It indicates that they review the code of the newcomers	Assign S19
Quote	11.42	Three codes B05, B13 and S07	3	It mentions how in some cases newcomers need time to know how things are done in the company	Assign S07 and B13
Quote	11.43	One code B01	1	Comments how newcomers on occasions are reluctant to ask	Assign B15
Quote	11.70	One code B01	1	Comments how newcomers on occasions are reluctant to ask	Assign B15
Quote	11.47	Three codes C03, S09 and S12	3	It mentions the types of tasks given to newcomers	Assign S09
Quote	11.71	Two codes B11 and Onboarding & Variability: specificities		It describes the process of incorporating the code to the platform. The difficulty is in the development itself.	Assign Onboarding & variability specificities
Quote	11.48	Three codes C13, S09 and Onboarding & Variability	3	It describes how today, the SPL is more mature and thus tasks are easier and more confined.	Assign C13 and Onboarding&Variability
Quote	11.50	Two codes S01 and S07	2	It describes how the exploration of code is	Assign S07

				aided by the mentor and how things are described to the newcomer	
Quote	11.52	Two codes S07 and Onboarding & Variability	3	It describes how they perform code reviews, S19 is more concrete.	Assign S19 and Onboarding&Variability
Quote	11.73	Two codes B01 and S09	3	It describes the types of tasks assigned to newcomers	Assign S09
Quote	11.60	Three codes C05, C12 and S02	3	It describes how they use Gitlab to cater for the development of the SPL	Assign C12